

STUDIES IN DEHYDROGENATION. PART VI.

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The synthesis and selenium dehydrogenation of 6:7-cyclopenteno-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane have been described. A rational synthesis of 2:3-cyclopenteno-phenanthrene has also been carried out.

In order to study selenium dehydrogenation of complex spiro-hydrocarbons, 6:7-cyclopenteno-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane has been synthesised. The anhydride of cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid has been condensed with hydrindene, forming primarily *aa*-cyclopentane- β -5-hydrindoylpropionic acid (I). The formation of trimellitic acid by the oxidation of this keto-acid with alkaline permanganate proves the linking of the keto group to 5 position of the hydrindene molecule. This keto-acid on reduction by the Clemmensen method gives *aa*-cyclopentane- γ -5-hydrindylbutyric acid (II), and the latter on cyclisation with 85% sulphuric acid gives 1-keto-6:7-cyclopenteno-1:2:3:4-

tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (III). The course of the cyclisation of the hydrindylbutyric acid (II) in forming the linear product (III), follows from the oxidation of the latter to 1:2:4:5-benzene-tetracarboxylic acid. The spiro-ketone (III) by Clemmensen reduction gives 6:7-cyclopenteno-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (IV).

It was expected that the spiro-hydrocarbon (IV) on selenium dehydrogenation would yield either 2:3-cyclopenteno-anthracene (VI) or 2:3-cyclo-

pentenophenanthrene (V) or both (*cf. J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 89, 349). In order to settle the constitution of the hydrocarbon obtained by dehydrogenation, a rational synthesis of 2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene has been carried out. The dehydrogenation product is found to be different from 2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene and is in all probability 2:3-cyclopenteno-anthracene.

The synthesis of 2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene has been carried out in the following manner. By the Friedel-Craft's reaction of the anhydride of Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid and naphthalene in nitrobenzene solution, a mixture of the isomeric keto-acids (VII) is obtained, from which the isomers could not be separated in a pure condition. The mixture of the keto-acids is reduced by Clemmensen's method giving a mixture of the isomeric naphthyl acids (VIII). An attempt to cyclise the mixture with 85% sulphuric acid at 100° resulted in a very poor yield of the

cyclisation product owing to extensive sulphonation, ring-closure being ultimately effected with zinc chloride at 180°. In the latter case an excellent yield of the cyclisation product, which was evidently a mixture of (IX, R=CH₂; R'=CO; IX, R=CO; R'=CH₂) is obtained. Clemmensen reduction of the mixture of ketocyclic compounds gives a homogeneous product namely 2:3-cyclopenteno-1:4-dihydrophenanthrene (IX, R=R'=CH₂). Selenium dehydrogenation of this hydrocarbon in a sealed tube at 300-310° gives a good yield of 2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene. It is obtained in a crystalline condition and readily yields a picrate and a trinitrobenzene complex which are different from the corresponding derivatives obtained from the dehydrogenation product of 6:7-cyclopenteno-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane.

EXPERIMENTAL.

α-cyclopentane-β-5-hydrindoylpropionic Acid (I).—It was prepared from hydrindene (24 g.), anhydride of cyclopentane-1-acetic-1-carboxylic acid (31 g.), aluminium chloride (52 g.) in nitrobenzene solution. The

mixture was kept in an ice-bath for 6 hours and at the ordinary temperature for 12 hours. After decomposition with ice and hydrochloric acid, excess of nitrobenzene and hydrindene were removed in steam. The solid product was extracted with sodium carbonate solution. It was crystallised first from glacial acetic acid and finally from rectified spirit in colourless needles, m.p. 140-41°. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 7.3. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 7.3 per cent).

The *methyl ester* distilled as a thick oil, b.p. 210-212°/5 mm., which slowly solidified on standing, m.p. 47-48°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 7.8. $C_{18}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 7.7 per cent).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid (I).—The keto-acid (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (5%, 100 c.c.) solution and heated on the water-bath with excess of potassium permanganate solution. After the excess of permanganate was destroyed with alcohol, the filtrate from the precipitated manganese dioxide was acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. It was extracted with ether, solvent removed and the residue crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid and identified as trimellitic acid, m.p. 214°.

α-cyclopentane-γ-5-hydrindylbutyric Acid (II).—*α-cyclopentane-β-5-hydrindylpropionic acid* (15 g.), amalgamated zinc (75 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (75 c.c.) were gently boiled for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, extract washed with water, solvent removed and the residue purified by distillation at 220°/6 mm. The distillate (11 g.) was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in hexagonal plates, m.p. 104.5°. (Found: C, 79.0; H, 8.5. $C_{17}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 79.1; H, 8.5 per cent)

6:7-cyclopenteno-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (III).—The foregoing hydrindylbutyric acid (7 g.) was cyclised by heating with 85% sulphuric acid (sulphuric acid 21 c.c. and water 7 c.c.) for 1½ hours on the steam-bath. The solid product was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in long prisms, m.p. 98-99°, yield 5.5 g. (Found: C, 85.07; H, 8.2. $C_{17}H_{20}O$ requires C, 85.0; H, 8.3 per cent).

The *oxidation of the spiro-ketone* (III) was carried out with alkaline permanganate solution as in the case of the oxidation of the keto-acid (I). The product was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid in needles and after drying in the air-bath at 100° was converted into its anhydride by heating with acetyl chloride. The anhydride was identical with the di-anhydride of 1:2:4:5-benzenetetracarboxylic acid, m.p. 284°.

6:7-cyclopenteno-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (IV).—The spiro-ketone (III) (4 g.) was heated with amalgamated zinc

(20 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) for 24 hours. The solid product was extracted with ether, solvent removed and the residue crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in colourless cubes, m.p. 64-65°, yield 2.8 g. (Found: C, 90.4; H, 9.6. $C_{17}H_{22}$ requires C, 90.3; H, 9.7 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.5 g.) was heated with powdered selenium (3 g.) in a metal-bath at 300-320° for 10 hours and at 340-350° for 30 hours. The product was thoroughly extracted with ether and petroleum ether. The liquid hydrocarbon obtained after distilling off the solvent, was distilled over sodium under reduced pressure when a liquid distillate (0.6 g.) was obtained. The hydrocarbon (0.3 g.) was converted into picrate in benzene solution and the dark orange picrate was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 149-50°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 3.9. $C_{23}H_{17}O_7N_3$ requires C, 61.8; H, 3.8 per cent).

The *trinitrobenzene complex* was prepared in benzene solution. It crystallised from alcohol in beautiful orange flakes, m.p. 128-29°. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 4.0. $C_{23}H_{17}O_6N_3$ requires C, 64.0; H, 3.9 per cent).

Synthesis of 2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene.— Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid, required for this synthesis, was prepared from ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate. The cyanohydrin of this keto-ester was prepared by the action of liquid hydrocyanic acid, and the corresponding unsaturated nitrile by dehydration with thionyl chloride. The nitrile on hydrolysis readily gave the required cyclopentenedicarboxylic acid.

Cyanohydrin of Ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate.—Ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (52 g.) was added to hydrocyanic acid (obtained from 65 g. of potassium cyanide), while cooled in a freezing mixture. A drop of potassium cyanide solution was added to the mixture and left overnight. The excess of hydrocyanic acid was removed under reduced pressure at the ordinary temperature and the crude cyanohydrin mixed with dry benzene (50 c.c.) and dried with sodium sulphate.

The benzene solution of the cyanohydrin was cooled in a freezing mixture and thionyl chloride (50 c.c.) was added drop by drop with constant stirring. After leaving overnight, the mixture was heated to boiling on the water-bath for 1 hour. It was then poured into ice, benzene layer was separated and the insoluble product extracted with benzene. The benzene solution was dried with calcium chloride and distilled. The fraction, b.p. 130°-140°/8 mm. was collected and redistilled at 133-135°/4 mm., the yield of the unsaturated nitrile ester being 25 g.

Hydrolysis of the Unsaturated Nitrile Ester.—The foregoing nitrile (20 g.) was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) for 2 hours, when

the oily layer disappeared. Water (50 c.c.) was added to this solution and the solution heated further for 5 hours. On cooling Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid crystallised out and was recrystallised from water, m.p. 178° (lit. 178°), yield 13 g. (Found: C, 53.6; H, 5.2. $C_7H_8O_4$ requires C, 53.8; H, 5.1 per cent).

Anhydride of Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid was obtained as a colourless liquid by boiling with acetic anhydride, b.p. $130^\circ/5$ mm.

Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1(α and β -naphthoyl)-2-carboxylic Acid (VII).—Aluminium chloride (34 g.) was added to an ice-cold solution of naphthalene (20 g.) and the anhydride of cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (17 g.) in nitrobenzene (100 c.c.). The product was worked up in the usual manner and after crystallisation from glacial acetic acid had m.p. $155-65^\circ$.

Clemmensen Reduction of the foregoing mixture of Keto-acids.—The mixture of the keto-acids (17 g.), amalgamated zinc (80 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (80 c.c.) was heated for 18 hours. The product was obtained as a thick liquid, b.p. $215-220^\circ/5$ mm. yield 12.5 g.

2:3-cyclopenteno-1,4-dihydrophenanthrene (IX, $R=R'=CH_2$).—The mixture of the naphthyl acids (VIII) (6.5 g.) was heated with fused powdered zinc chloride (15 g.) at 180° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the product was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with dilute ammonia and water and solvent distilled off. The oily residue (5 g.) was directly reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (25 g.) and hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.) for 18 hours. The product was distilled under reduced pressure when the distillate readily solidified. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. $50-60^\circ$) in thick plates, m.p. $101-2^\circ$, yield 2.6 g. (Found: C, 92.5; H, 7.4. $C_{17}H_{16}$ requires C, 92.7; H, 7.3 per cent).

2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene (V).—The foregoing hydrocarbon (2 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with selenium (2 g.) at $300-320^\circ$ for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, solvent distilled off and the crystalline residue was distilled over sodium under reduced pressure, yield 1.6 g.

The trinitrobenzene complex was prepared from the hydrocarbon (0.3 g.) and trinitrobenzene (0.3 g.) in alcoholic solution. The additive compound crystallised from alcohol in fine yellow silky needles, m.p. $162-63^\circ$. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 3.9. $C_{23}H_{17}O_3N_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 3.9 per cent).

The picrate crystallised from alcohol in golden yellow needles, m.p. 157° . (Found: C, 61.7; H, 3.9. $C_{23}H_{17}O_7N_3$ requires C, 61.8; H, 3.8 per cent).

Pure 2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene was regenerated from the picrate by decomposition with ammonium hydroxide. It crystallised from methyl

alcohol in stout needles, m.p. 84° . (Found: C, 93.5; H, 6.4. $C_{17}H_{14}$ requires C, 93.6; H, 6.4 per cent).

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